

Solving First-Order Differential Equation in Computational Physics Based on Fourth-Order Runge-Kutta Method with C Language

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Abstract: In the paper, I study how to solve first-order differential equation in computational physics based on the fourth order Runge-Kutta method with C language. Firstly, first-order ordinary differential equation is briefly introduced from the perspectives of mathematical concept and physical significance. Secondly, the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method is elaborated. Then, combining C language with the above algorithm, a concrete application is presented to bring out this process. Finally, the advantages of C language in solving the problem based on fourth-order Runge-Kutta are summarized.

Keywords: C language; First-order ordinary differential equation; Numerical method; Fourth order Runge-Kutta method.

I. Introduction

Computational physics has been an important branch of physics, which mainly studies how to use computers to simulate the behavior of physical system. In computational physics, differential equations are usually mathematical models describing physical system. Therefore, solving differential equations is a basic task. However, in many cases, differential equations cannot be solved analytically so that it requires the use of numerical method. Therefore, this paper will study on how to use C language^[1] to solve the first-order Ordinary differential equation based on fourth order Runge-Kutta method.

The outline of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 gives a brief account of the mathematical and physical significance of first-order ordinary differential equations. Section 3 presents the basic content of fourth-order Runge-kutta method. In Section 4, a concrete application is given to realize the entire process. A conclusion is drawn in Section 5.

II. First-order Ordinary Differential Equations

First-order ordinary differential equations are a fundamental tool widely used in mathematics and physics, and can be used to describe many natural phenomena and physical processes. The numerical method is an important tool for solving first-order ordinary differential equations, which can solve differential equations through computer simulation to obtain numerical solutions.

2.1 Mathematical concept

A first-order ordinary differential equation contains only a derivative of an unknown function, and the general form is

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = f(x, y)$$

where y is the unknown function, x is the argument, and $f(x, y)$ is the known function.

2.2 Physical significance

The physical meaning of a first-order ordinary differential equation is to describe the law of the change of which a physical quantity changes with an independent variable. For example, in a RL circuit, the change in current magnitude over time can be expressed as a first-order ordinary differential equation:

$$L \frac{di}{dt} + Ri = V$$

Where i is the current in the circuit, t is time, L is the inductor, R is the resistance, and V is the voltage.

III. Fourth-Order Runge-Kutta

Runge-Kutta method is one of the most commonly used numerical methods for solving ordinary differential equations (ODEs)^[2,3]. It can solve various forms of ODEs such as first-order, multi-order, and ordinary differential equations. As it has high precision, good stability and wide range of application, it is widely used in scientific and engineering calculations.

The basic idea is to treat the solution on ODEs as the tangent slope at the initial value point of the ODEs, and according to the tangent slope at the initial value point, through a series of iterative calculations, the approximate solution of the ODE at the next time step is obtained^[4].

The Runge-Kutta method is to obtain the approximate solution of ODEs by performing tangent calculations on multiple points on ODEs and fourth-order Runge-Kutta method (RK4) is used commonly. The RK4 is to treat the solution on the ODE as the tangent slope at the initial value point of the ODEs, and then solve the next state through the four slopes and the current state according to the tangent slope at the initial value point^[5,6]. Specifically, the iteration formula of the RK4 is as follows

$$\begin{cases} y_{i+1} = y_i + \frac{h}{6}(K_1 + 2K_2 + 2K_3 + K_4) \\ K_1 = f(x_i, y_i) \\ K_2 = f(x_i + \frac{h}{2}, y_i + \frac{h}{2}K_1) \\ K_3 = f(x_i + \frac{h}{2}, y_i + \frac{h}{2}K_2) \\ K_4 = f(x_i + h, y_i + hK_3) \end{cases}$$

where h represents the step size selected during calculation, K_1 represents the slope at point x_i , K_2 represents the slope at point $x_i + \frac{h}{2}$ according to K_1 , K_3 represents the slope at the $(x_i + \frac{h}{2})$ point from K_2 , K_4 represents the slope at the $(x_i + h)$ point from K_3 .

The accuracy of this method is high so a more accurate approximate solution can usually be obtained when solving ODEs. However, it should be noted that the RK4 method has a

large amount of calculation, so it is necessary to trade off accuracy and computational efficiency in practical application.

IV. Concrete Application

4.1 Problem descriptions and mathematical models

Supposing a particle vibrates harmonically under the action of elastic force without damping. The change in the displacement x of a particle with time t satisfies the following differential equation

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = -\frac{k}{m}x \quad (1)$$

where k is the elastic coefficient of the spring, m is the mass of a particle.

To solve the differential equation (1), we can convert it into two first-order differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = v \\ \frac{dv}{dt} = -\frac{k}{m}x \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

4.2 Programming and implementation

This section is trying to use the RK4 to analyses and solve system (2). The specific steps are as follows:

1) Define ordinary differential equations: ordinary differential equations that need to be solved are expressed as a function, such as void f(double t, double y[], double dydt[]), where t is time, y[] is the state vector, and dydt[] is the derivative of the state vector.

The specific C language^[7,8] procedure is as follows.

// Define the ordinary differential equation dx/dt=f(t,x,v), where v is the velocity

```
void f(double t, double x, double v, double f[])
```

```
{
```

```
    double k = 1.0, m=1.0; // Elastic coefficient and quality of the particle
```

```
    f[0] = v;
```

```
    f[1] = -k/m*x; // Ordinary differential equations for simple harmonic
```

vibrations

```
}
```

2) Define the initial conditions: determine the initial time t0 and the initial state vector y0[].

3) Define time step: Select the appropriate time step h=0.01 to calculate the state of each time step.

4) Iteration using the RK4^[9]: iterate at each time step and calculate an approximation of the state vector. The commonly formula is as follows

$$\begin{cases} K_1 = h * f(t_i, y_i) \\ K_2 = h * f(t_i + h/2, y_i + K_1/2) \\ K_3 = h * f(t_i + h, y_i + K_2/2) \\ K_4 = h * f(t_i + h, y_i + K_3) \\ y_{i+1} = y_i + (K_1 + 2K_2 + 2K_3 + K_4)/6 \end{cases}$$

where K_1, K_2, K_3 and K_4 are the four slopes, $f(t, y)$ is the ordinary differential equation, y_i is the current state vector, t_i is the current time.

The specific C language^[10] procedure is as follows:

```
// One-step solution using the RK4. void rk4(double t, double x[], double h)
{
    double f1[2], f2[2], f3[2], f4[2], k1[2], k2[2], k3[2], k4[2];
    int i;
    f(t, x[0], x[1], f1);
    for (i = 0; i < 2; i++)
    {
        k1[i] = h * f1[i];
        k2[i] = h * f1[i] + k1[i] / 2.0;
        k3[i] = h * f1[i] + k2[i] / 2.0;
        k4[i] = h * f1[i] + k3[i];
        x[i] += (k1[i] + 2.0 * k2[i] + 2.0 * k3[i] + k4[i]) / 6.0;
    }
}
```

5) Cyclic iteration: selection using the RK4 method at each time step until the desired point is reached, such as the end time t_n .

The specific C language procedure is as follows
while ($t < t_n$)

```
{
    rk4(t, x, h);
    t += h;
}
```

6) Output result: Output the state vector of each time step to obtain an approximate solution.

The solution of the simple harmonic vibration is achieved here. The initial conditions are $x(0) = 0$ and $\frac{dx}{dt}|_{t=0} = v(0) = 1$. In the rk4 functions, the next state is solved according to these four slopes marked K_1, K_2, K_3 and K_4 and the current state. In the main function, by constantly calling the rk4 function, solve the values of x and v from $t=0$ to $t=3.8$, and then output the state of each step.

4.3 Results analysis and discussion

Fig. 1. Velocity-time curve

Fig. 2. Displacement-time curve

The output results from this program can be used to analyze the behavior of simple harmonic vibrations. In Fig.1, The relationship between the velocity and time of simple harmonic vibration is a cosine function, that is, the velocity changes with the cosine of time. In Fig.2, The relationship between the displacement and time of simple harmonic vibration is a sinusoidal function, that is, the displacement changes sinusoidally with time.

V. Conclusion

The paper has studied how to solve first-order differential equation in computational physics based on fourth order Runge-Kutta method by C language. It can be seen that solving first-order ordinary differential equations in C language can make the whole solution process simple and efficient, and the application area is wide, providing a practical tool for computational physics research.

References

- [1] H.Y. Chen, Research on On-Line Programming Code Defect Detection System Based on C Language, *Information & Computer*, 2023, 2: 130-133.
- [2] E. Hairer, S.P. Norsett, G. Wanner, *Solving Ordinary Differential Equations I*, Springer, Berlin, 1993.
- [3] J.D. Lambert, *Numerical Methods for Ordinary Differential Systems*, Wiley, England, 1991.
- [4] Ibrahim Almuslimani, Nicolas Crouseilles, Conservative stabilized Runge-Kutta methods for the Vlasov-Fokker-Planck equation, *Journal of Computational Physics*, 2023, 488: 112241.
- [5] J.C. Butcher, *Numerical Methods for Ordinary Differential Equations*, Wiley, Chichester, England, 2003.
- [6] J.I. Montijano, L. Rández, M. Calvo, Explicit Runge-Kutta methods for the numerical solution of linear inhomogeneous IVPs, *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, 2023, 425:115083.
- [7] Q. Lu, Design of Multiple Loop Structure in C Language Computer Engineering, 2023, 52(03): 32-33.
- [8] M. Piteira and C. Costa, Learning computer programming: Study of difficulties in learning programming, *Proc. Int. Conf. Inf. Syst. Des. Commun.*, 75-80, 2013: 75-80.
- [9] Shinhoo Kang, Alp Dener, Aidan Hamilton, Hong Zhang, Emil M. Constantinescu, Robert L. Jacob, Multirate partitioned Runge-Kutta methods for coupled Navier-Stokes equations, *Computers & Fluids*, 2023, 264: 105964.
- [10] S.L. Chen, L.Y. Liu, Discussion of the Usefulness of Debug Techniques in Teaching of C Programming Language, *Computer Knowledge and Technology*, 2015, 11(24): 80-82.